

PROTOSTACK short presentation

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1 Goal and consortium

Proton conducting ceramic electrolyser (PCCEL) is an emerging electrolysis technology with potential for inherently *higher efficiency* compared to commercial electrolysers based on Alkaline and PEM technologies due to the higher operating temperature. PCCEL can also offer higher efficiency than solid oxide electrolysers (SOEL) as the produced hydrogen is not diluted by steam and therefore doesn't require downstream separation.¹ Furthermore, the efficiency of PCCEL *benefits from pressurized operation* due to enhanced hydration of the proton ceramic phases present in the cells and improved gas exchange kinetics, contributing to lower area specific resistance.² The possibility to operate under pressure and deliver pressurized hydrogen is a huge advantage as storage, transport, and industrial use of hydrogen requires hydrogen pressure extending from a few bar (e.g. steel processes), to several dozen bar for grid injection and refinery plants, and as high as 300-700 bar in refuelling stations. Hydrogen compression is commonly achieved in three mechanical compression stages, with the first stage that delivers 10-30 bar being the least efficient² and costly due to the need for large volume compressors. Avoiding this first stage compressor would thus greatly *reduce the overall cost of hydrogen*, in addition to reducing the size and complexity of the hydrogen production plant.

PROTOSTACK will create a radically new, compact and modular PCCEL stack design with integrated hotbox for operation and delivery of hydrogen up to 30 bar. The stack will be demonstrated at 5kW and provide a pathway for further scale-up to systems of hundreds of kW. These achievements will be an important proof of technological feasibility that will attest to the advancement of PCCEL technology from TRL 2 to TRL 4.

To achieve its ambitious goal, the project consortium gathers research and industry partners that are world-leading within proton ceramic technologies, with recognized expertise relevant to the research and development of electrolysers, membrane-reactors, materials, electrochemistry, and process engineering. The overall consortium will engage in wide communication and dissemination activities to ensure maximum impact of the project's outcomes and the industry partners have high ambition for business exploitation and commercialisation of the PROTOSTACK technology.

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	SINTEF AS	SINTEF	NO
2	Shell Global Solutions International BV	Shell	NL
3	CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS	CTMS	NO
4	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas	CSIC	ES
5	ATENA SCARL – Distretto Alta Tecnologia Energia Ambiente	ATENA	IT
6	DEMCON energy systems B.V.	DEMCON	NL

¹ J.M. Serra, Nature Energy 4 (2019), 178-179

² E. Vøllestad et al, Nature Materials 18 (2019), 752-759

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2 PROTOSTACK objectives

The project aims to demonstrate the competitive advantage of Pressurized Proton Ceramic Electrolysis (PCCEL) technology. The central concept of PROTOSTACK is a new stack technology with tolerance for high pressure operation, and experimentally demonstrate its operation up to 30 bar in a 5kW stack panel.

The stack design is based on a tubular cell architecture, which is **inherently better suited for pressurized operation** compared to planar stacks and offers possibility for **operation under differential pressures**. The basic design of the stack concept is illustrated in figure 1. The novel **compact and modular** technology will be based on a ca. 400W **stack**, which can be easily replicated and assembled in multiple **stack panels** to build up capacity.

The project will demonstrate capacity of 5kW. Each stack will consist of up to six Single Repeating Units (**SRU**), electrically connected in series using a *specialized interconnect and integrated glass ceramic sealant*. Each SRU will contain 6 *tubular proton ceramic-based cells* and other key enabling technologies (**KETs**) such as interconnects and seals.

The short length of the individual cells and a *specialized current collector system integrated with each electrode* will alleviate current collection challenges encountered in tubular systems. All processes will be aligned with a sustainable value chain for stack manufacturing based on eco-design principles targeting reduced emissions and consumption of energy and critical raw materials.

Figure 1. Stack concept in PROTOSTACK. Illustration of Key Enabling Technologies (KET), Single repeating unit (SRU) and stack panels.

The stack design will integrate *electrical feedthroughs, gas manifolds and a steel pressure vessel* (not shown in the figures for clarity). An important aspect of this design, compared to the contiguous planar stacks, lies in its *improved robustness towards thermal gradients and thermal runaway propagation* owing to its geometrical configuration.

This stack design will be easily amenable to higher capacity by assembling the stacks in panels. The project will establish the necessary knowledge and know-how to develop and demonstrate a scaled-up version of this technology, represented by a *5kW stack panel containing 13 stacks fully integrated*

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in a hotbox with necessary manifolds for gas supply and electrical connections, as well as insulation and power electronics. The arrangement of the stacks in the hotbox will be optimised for highest electrical efficiency and thermal management.

The hotbox will be designed to be operational also with lower number of stacks as a risk mitigation measure to progressively furnish and test the 5kW stack panel in a complete system. This novel technology will create **innovations in electrochemical stack design, stack components, processing methods for stack assembly** and hands-on knowledge on pressurized PCCEL technology.

The project outcomes aim at the following aspects:

- Demonstration on stack level of a pressurized steam electrolysis solution by 2025
- Reduction of CAPEX to 2000 €/(kg/d) and OPEX to 130 €/(kg/d)/y
- Reduction of the life-cycle environmental footprint of electrolyzers Improved performance, achieving current density of 0.5 A/cm², Faradaic operation of at least 90% and pressure at stack level of 30 bar

3 Additional information

Project start and duration: 01/01/2023 – 3 years

European funding contribution: ca. 2.5 M€

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